

Geomorphological Features and Vegetation Types Analysis of Pasturelands Using DEM

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Abstract

This study focuses on the geomorphological and vegetation zoning of pastures in the Bostanliq district using a Digital Elevation Model (DEM). Based on elevation, the territory was divided into four main geomorphological zones: foothill pastures (500–1000 m), piedmont pastures (1000–1200 m), mountain pastures (1200–2500 m), and high-mountain pastures (above 2500 m). According to the analysis, the total pasture area covers 187,833 ha, of which 48,785.26 ha belong to foothill pastures, 44,911.27 ha to piedmont pastures, 83,830.58 ha to mountain pastures, and 10,305.89 ha to high-mountain pastures. Each geomorphological zone is characterized by distinct vegetation types reflecting differences in altitude, climate, and soil conditions. The integration of DEM-based zoning with vegetation analysis provides a comprehensive scientific basis for sustainable pasture use, monitoring of ecological changes, and the development of management strategies adapted to local natural conditions.

Keywords: Pasturelands, Geomorphological zoning, Vegetation types, Digital Elevation Model (DEM), GIS analysis, Bostanliq district, Sustainable pasture management, Mountain ecosystems, Remote sensing, Ecological assessment.

INTRODUCTION

Pasture ecosystems play a vital role in ensuring livestock productivity and maintaining ecological balance in mountainous regions. However, due to excessive grazing, land degradation, and lack of scientific management, pasture areas in Uzbekistan, particularly in the Tashkent region, face serious challenges. Effective use of pastures requires a precise understanding of their geomorphological characteristics and vegetation distribution. Digital Elevation Models (DEM) provide a modern geoinformation tool that enables accurate delineation of relief-based zones. At the same time, identifying vegetation types in each zone makes it possible to assess the ecological potential of pastures and develop management strategies adapted to natural conditions [1-2]. The Bustanlik district is one of the largest pasture regions in Tashkent province, characterized by diverse relief conditions ranging from foothills to high mountains. These variations directly influence vegetation cover, soil properties, and the productivity of grazing lands. *So far, detailed geomorphological mapping of pastures based on DEM and comprehensive classification of vegetation types in the territory of Bustanlik district have not been carried out in scientific research.* Therefore, the main aim of this research is to analyze the geomorphological zoning of pastures in the Bustanlik district using DEM and to identify the dominant vegetation types in each zone. The findings of this study are expected to contribute to sustainable pasture management, ecological monitoring, and the development of evidence-based land-use strategies in Uzbekistan.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The scientific and ecologically sustainable use of pasture lands is one of the key factors in preserving the forage base and increasing efficiency in livestock farming today. According to the current legislation, pasture lands are classified as agricultural lands and are legally managed as a separate category. However, in practice, they are often evaluated as a single type of “pasture,” without considering their diverse ecological and territorial characteristics, which causes numerous problems [8].

According to Article 9 of the Land Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, lands are divided into categories based on their primary use, and this is reflected in land cadastre documents. This provision establishes the legal framework for defining

the purpose of land use, as well as for its management and protection. Therefore, it is essential to classify pasture lands not only as a single category but also by taking into account their natural-geographical and ecological characteristics. Such classification makes it possible, on the one hand, to determine the load and restrictions for each pasture zone, and on the other hand, to prevent their degradation.

The concept of sustainable pasture use requires compliance with ecological conditions of the land, as well as consideration of socio-economic needs for the population's livelihood and farming activities. Harmonious development of society presupposes the coordination of natural and technological systems. Hence, socio-economic challenges, which are closely connected with ecological and economic problems, should be addressed as a priority.

According to A.R. Babajonov, the first priority in the use of pastures in Uzbekistan is their regionalization and zoning. Based on natural conditions, pastures of the country are divided into desert, foothill (adir), mountain, and high-mountain zones [3].

It should be noted that the government of Uzbekistan has taken significant measures to improve the situation in pasture management [5]. For example, the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers and, in particular, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-219 dated December 28, 2023, "On the State Program for the Digitalization of Land Resource Management and the Use of Pastures", are among the most important policy initiatives. In pasture areas, relief factors play an important role in determining the distribution and area of vegetation types [4]. This is because parameters such as elevation, slope, and aspect directly influence the density and spatial arrangement of plant cover. Therefore, before using remote sensing data, it is necessary to identify the main characteristics of the terrain. One of the most widely used tools for this purpose is the Digital Elevation Model (DEM) (FIGURE 1).

FIGURE 1. The elevation data were derived from open-source Digital Elevation Model (DEM) sources.

DEM datasets are freely accessible through open sources, with the most commonly used being SRTM (Shuttle Radar Topography Mission), ASTER GDEM (Advanced Spaceborne Thermal Emission and Reflection Radiometer Global DEM), and Copernicus DEM. Their resolution varies between 90 meters and 30 meters, and the appropriate option is selected depending on the purpose of scientific analysis. In this study, the selected DEM data were imported in raster format into the ArcGIS software for further processing (FIGURE 2).

FIGURE 2. The Digital Elevation Model (DEM) of the Bostanliq district was generated using ArcGIS software.

Initially, it was essential to delimit the study area by extracting only the pasture zone from the total territory. This procedure was performed in ArcGIS using the “Clip Raster” and “Extract by Mask” functions, which enabled the removal of irrelevant data and the preservation of the target region. Subsequently, potential errors in the raster dataset, such as artificial depressions (“sinks”) in low-lying areas, were corrected through the “Fill” function to ensure hydrological consistency [5].

In the following stage, terrain parameters were derived to characterize the relief of the study area. The “Spatial Analyst Tools → Surface” module in ArcGIS was employed to generate a set of derivative maps, including:

- Slope map – quantifying the steepness of the terrain;
- Aspect map – indicating the directional orientation of slopes;
- Hillshade map – producing a three-dimensional shaded relief visualization [6].

These topographic derivatives significantly enhance both visual interpretation and quantitative analysis. In particular, they provide valuable insights into the spatial distribution of pasturelands across elevation zones, slope gradients, and their exposure to solar radiation, which are crucial factors for evaluating pasture suitability and degradation risks [7].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

According to the State Cadastre Chamber under the Cadastre Agency of the Ministry of Economy and Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as of January 1, 2024, the total land area of Tashkent region amounts to 1,514,926 hectares. Among this, Bustanliq district accounts for 493,421 hectares, representing approximately 33% of the regional territory. Within the district’s land resources, pasturelands cover 187,833 hectares. The distribution of these pasture areas across different elevation zones is presented in the following table (Table1)

Table-1

Distribution of Pasturelands in Bostanliq District by Elevation Zones

Pasture zones	Elevation range (m)	Pasture area by zones (ha)
Foothill pastures	500-1000	48 785,26
Piedmont pastures	1000-1200	44 911,27
Mountain pastures	1200-2500	83 830,58
High mountain pastures	2500+	10 305,89
Total pasture area:		187 833,0

Note: Elevation data were derived from open-source DEM (Digital Elevation Model) datasets and processed in ArcGIS software.

Bustanliq District is located in the northeastern part of Tashkent Region and represents one of the most fertile natural landscapes of the mountainous areas of Central Asia. The district’s relief is characterized by a complex morphological structure, with the main part occupied by the Chatkal, Ugam, and Piskom mountain ranges belonging to the Western Tien Shan system. A relief map generated from the Digital Elevation Model (DEM) clearly demonstrates the steepness of the

elevation gradients, with mountain slopes varying between 10° and 45°. The eastern and southeastern sectors are situated at elevations ranging from 2,500 to 4,300 meters, where extensive high-mountain meadows are widely developed [9].

FIGURE 3: Digital modeling of the relief of Bostanliq District and its morphometric indicators based on geospatial data.

In the process of pasture zoning, the natural conditions, relief, and soil–climatic characteristics of each territory were taken into account, and their exact areas were calculated. As a result of these calculations, the distribution of pastures across desert, foothill, mountain foothill, and mountain zones was determined. The total area of each zone was measured using GIS tools and subsequently visualized on maps.

However, a comprehensive characterization of pasture ecosystems cannot be limited to area measurements alone. Therefore, the study also examined the types of vegetation distributed across these zones.

Furthermore, according to the implementation of the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 23, 2018, No. 299, “On improving the procedure for defining the boundaries of administrative-territorial units, inventorying land resources, and conducting geobotanical surveys in pastures and hayfields,” geobotanical investigations were carried out in the pasture lands of Bostanliq District by the State Scientific Design Institute *Uzdavyerloyiha* under the Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan (Figure4)

FIGURE 4. Distribution of vegetation types

In my research, I also analyzed the 2018 geobotanical survey reports and maps conducted by the State Scientific Design Institute “Uzdavyerloyiha,” since the floristic composition of pastures played an important role in delineating pasture regions within the district. The study of relief, climate, and vegetation cover is essential for developing prospective land management plans, particularly in the context of reforming the livestock production system and ensuring the sustainable use of pasture resources. As part of the research, I thoroughly examined the vegetation type attributes within the polygon layers of the pasture areas and calculated the mean, minimum, and maximum values of the Digital Elevation Model (DEM) and its derived layers for each vegetation type polygon (Table2)

Table-2

Pasture types of Bustonlik district by ecological zones and their respective areas (hectares)

Pasture zones	Plant types	Pasture area (ha)
Foothill pastures (500-1000)	169	986,46
	205	1096,6
	221	244,78
	223	1064,89
	224	12460,67
	225	4068,84
	226	814,85
	237	2679,82
	242	251,02
	244	9286,8
	245	1939,39
	247	4863,9
	248	251,31
	249	1831,33
	250	447,42
257	1199,05	
259	473,99	
260	4106,57	
261	687,96	
265	29,61	
Total:		48 785,26
Piedmont pastures (1000-1200)	223	2098,36
	224	4493,84
	225	636,93
	226	1542,61
	237	13,06
	242	705,73
	244	4147,28
	244a	755,66
	245	2255,76
	247	4160,94
	248	1205,94
	249	593,67
	250	2269,9
	257	3765,62
	259	5343,17
260	8959,11	
261	135,07	
264	576,25	
265	86,76	
274	1165,61	
Total:		44 911,27
Mountain pastures (1200-2500 metr)	223	3181,86
	224	381,44

	226	418,39
	242	43,86
	244	18584,03
	244a	98,98
	245	4449,29
	247	3117,42
	248	138,89
	249	28,2
	250	1347,7
	257	3841,95
	259	6909,39
	260	12120,21
	261	139,67
	264	21,31
	265	3,61
	274	4342,41
	276	21300,23
	287	3361,74
Total:		83 830,58
High mountain pastures (2500 metr dan yuqori)	260	2916,46
	276	7389,43
Total:		10 305,89
Total pasture area:		187 833,00

As presented in the table, the pastures of Bustonlik district were classified according to their ecological zones, and their respective areas were determined.

CONCLUSION

This study highlights the importance of applying geoinformation technologies, particularly Digital Elevation Models (DEM) and GIS-based analyses, in the classification and assessment of pasture resources in Bustonlik district. By integrating relief parameters such as elevation, slope, and aspect with vegetation distribution data, a detailed spatial differentiation of pastures was achieved. The results demonstrated that pastures in the district are distributed across four main ecological zones: desert, foothill, mountain, and high-mountain, covering a total of 187,833 hectares. Each ecological zone exhibits distinctive vegetation types and areas, which were quantified and mapped for the first time with high precision.

The use of geobotanical survey reports (2018) in combination with DEM-derived morphometric indicators enabled a comprehensive evaluation of vegetation–relief relationships. This integrated approach not only allows for more accurate monitoring of pasture ecosystems but also provides a scientific basis for sustainable land management and livestock development strategies.

Overall, the findings confirm that reliance solely on general “pasture” classifications without considering geomorphological and ecological diversity leads to inefficiencies in pasture use and potential degradation. Therefore, scientifically grounded regionalization of pastures is essential for ensuring their ecological stability, improving forage productivity, and supporting long-term rural development planning in Uzbekistan.

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